

Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarins with primary aromatic amines and alcohols : A new efficient route to access direct C-N bond *via* monobenzylation of 3-aminocoumarin derivatives

Nazia Kausar and Asish R. Das*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : ardchem@caluniv.ac.in, ardas66@rediffmail.com *Fax* : 91-33-23519754

Manuscript received 07 December 2017, revised 09 January 2018, accepted 16 January 2017

Abstract : Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarin derivatives has been accomplished employing benzylamine and benzylalcohol as benzylation agent. In contrast to the conventional methodologies employing precious metal catalysis and hazardous benzyl bromide reagent, the use of earth-abundant metal catalyst and aromatic amines or alcohols as direct benzylation agents is generally an attractive and less hazardous process for benzylation of 3-aminocoumarin derivatives. Developed synthetic protocol offers various advantages like operational simplicity, inexpensive metal catalyst, relatively lower thermal energy and a high product yield. It is noteworthy to mention that N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarin is limited to monobenzylation step keeping away from the possibility of over alkylation.

Keywords : 3-Aminocoumarins, N-benylation, C-N bond formation, benzylalcohol, benzylamine, copper acetate, monobenzylation.

Introduction

Formation of carbon-nitrogen bonds under catalytic condition¹⁻³ is a topic of great interest since nitrogen functionalities occur in various compounds of synthetic and pharmaceutical significance as well as in important biologically active molecules⁴. Mostly precious metal (Pd, Ru, Ir) catalysis has been employed to achieve crucial organic transformations including some C-C and C-N bond-forming reactions⁵. Advantage of the precious metal catalysis includes high catalytic activity and turnover frequencies⁵. However, the scarcity, cost, and toxicity of precious metals can make the chemical transformation less attractive for widespread and large-scale commercial applications in industry. In recent years, the replacement of precious metal catalysts with earth-abundant metal has become an intensive research topic, in consideration of synthetic organic chemistry⁶.

The alkylation reaction of amines is typically

achieved by reaction with an alkyl halide, although this procedure can arise complications due to over alkylation and the toxic nature of many alkyl halides and related alkylating agents⁷. The use of amines and alcohols as direct alkylating agents for amines is generally a less hazardous process than the use of conventional alkylating agents due to high stability, relatively high atom efficiency and low toxicity of alcohol and amines.

In recent years many methodologies were developed for alkylation of amines. Beller and co-workers described ruthenium catalyzed N-alkylation of anilines with aliphatic amines⁸. Zheng *et al.* demonstrated 'a borrowing hydrogen strategy' for N-alkylation of aliphatic amines⁹. The alkylation of primary amines using alcohols has been described by Williams *et al.*¹⁰. Moreover, air-promoted ruthenium catalyzed N-alkylation reaction of amides and amines with alcohols was established by Xu and co-workers¹¹.

Fig. 1. Some naturally occurring potent alkaloids and biologically active 3-aminocoumarin structural unit.

However, benzylation of 3-aminocoumarin system with alcohol and amines are not revealed in literature till date. 3-Aminocoumarin and its derivatives are one of the most active classes of compounds possessing a wide range of biological activity¹². Due to their wide spectrum of biological activities, various research groups have put their efforts to synthesize compounds containing 3-aminocoumarin structural core¹³ (Fig. 1). It has been reported that the C₃-N-substituted coumarins are active pharmaceutical ingredients and were used as important intermediates to construct highly conjugated structures¹⁴. Moreover, C₃-N-benzylated coumarin derivatives were found to exhibit anticancer activities against

MGC-803, A549, and NCI-H460 cell lines¹⁵. However, there are only a few methods to synthesize C₃-N-substituted coumarins¹⁷. Previously benzylation of 3-aminocoumarin were done either by using benzylbromide as benzylating agent¹⁶ or Pd catalyzed Buchwald Hartwig amination (Scheme 1)¹⁷. The main disadvantages of the above mentioned protocols include low yield, requirement of expensive metal catalysts, prolonged heating (24–30 h) and use of hazardous benzylating agent. Thus an alternative and competent strategy to achieve N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarin is highly desirable. In continuation of our recent effort to synthesize biologically relevant compounds containing 3-aminocoumarin

Scheme 1. Various alkylation processes of amines and 3-aminocoumarin derivatives.

Kausar *et al.* : Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarins with primary aromatic *etc.*

structural unit¹⁸, we wish to report a Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarin applying benzyl amine and benzyl alcohol as benzylating agent.

Experimental

Materials and method : All reagents were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification, unless otherwise specified. Commercially supplied ethyl acetate and petroleum ether were distilled before use. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (100–200 mesh, 0.12–0.25 mm). Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on 0.25 mm extra-hard silica gel plates with a UV254 fluorescent indicator. The reported melting points are uncorrected. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at ambient temperature using 300 MHz spectrometers (300 MHz for ¹H and 75 MHz for ¹³C). Chemical shifts were reported in parts per million from the tetramethylsilane internal reference, and coupling constants were reported in Hertz. Proton multiplicities were represented as s (singlet), d (doublet), dd (double doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), and m (multiplet). Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pallets in reflection mode on a FTIR spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were done using an automated CHNS analyzer. Mass spectra (ESI-MS) were recorded on Waters Xevo G-2-SQ TOF electrospray ionization mass spectrophotometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of pyridocoumarins : 3-Aminocoumarin (1 mmol), benzylamine/benzylalcohol (1.2 mmol), Cu(OAc)₂ (10 mol%), NaN₃ (2 equiv.) were heated in HOAc (1 ml) at 80°C. After completion of reaction (indicated by TLC), the reaction mixture was treated with cold saturated NaHCO₃ solution and then extracted with ethyl acetate (2×3 ml). Solvent (EtOAc) removal followed by column chromatography (eluent : ethyl acetate/petroleum ether 1 : 9) led to the pure products. All compounds were well characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR and FT-IR analysis.

Characterization data of compound (3a-3l) :

3-(Benzylamino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3a) : Molecular formula : C₁₆H₁₃NO₂; white solid (0.216 g, 86%); m.p. 160–162°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 4.42 (d, 2H, *J* = 5.7 Hz), 5.36 (s, 1H), 6.35 (s, 1H), 7.19–7.33 (m, 5H), 7.35–7.40 (m, 4H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 47.45, 105.65, 116.06, 121.57, 124.60, 125.12, 125.84, 127.30, 127.68, 128.83, 132.84, 137.24, 147.99, 159.89; IR (KBr) : 3304, 3099, 1758, 1549 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃NO₂ : [M+H]⁺, 252.1019; Found : *m/z* 252.1018.

3-((4-Methylbenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3b) : Molecular formula : C₁₇H₁₅NO₂; white solid (0.219 g, 83%); m.p. 130–132°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 2.39 (s, 3H), 4.42 (d, 2H, *J* = 5.4 Hz), 5.29 (s, 1H), 6.36 (s, 1H), 7.15 (t, 1H, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 7.26–7.42 (m, 6H), 7.75 (d, 1H, *J* = 7.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 21.05, 47.43, 105.60, 116.01, 121.51, 124.58, 125.05, 125.68, 127.24, 127.62, 128.76, 132.80, 137.22, 147.79, 159.78; IR (KBr) : 3309, 3085, 1762 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅NO₂ : [M+H]⁺, 266.1176; Found : *m/z* 266.1176.

3-((4-Chlorobenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3c) : Molecular formula : C₁₆H₁₂ClNO₂; white solid (0.253 g, 88%); m.p. 160–162°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 4.38 (s, 2H), 5.38 (s, 1H), 6.45 (s, 1H), 7.33–7.38 (m, 4H), 7.43 (m, 2H, *J* = 8.4 Hz), 7.55 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 47.45, 105.66, 116.06, 121.57, 124.60, 125.12, 125.84, 127.30, 127.67, 128.83, 132.27, 137.22, 148.28, 160.12; IR (KBr) : 3307, 3089, 1757 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂ClNO₂ : [M+H]⁺, 286.0629; Found : *m/z* 286.0628.

3-((4-Methoxybenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3d) : Molecular formula : C₁₇H₁₅NO₃; pale yellow solid (0.239 g, 85%); m.p. 125–127°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 3.66 (s, 3H), 4.27 (s, 2H), 5.29 (s, 1H), 6.59 (s, 1H), 7.19 (d, 2H, *J* =

7.2 Hz), 7.29 (t, 2H, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 7.46–7.52 (m, 4H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 47.12, 56.16, 105.32, 115.73, 121.23, 124.27, 124.79, 125.50, 126.97, 127.35, 128.50, 132.48, 136.89, 147.37, 158.27; IR (KBr): 3313, 3088, 1767 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$: C, 72.58; H, 5.37; N, 4.98%. Found: C, 72.61; H, 5.39; N, 5.01%.

3-(Benzylamino)-8-methoxy-2H-chromen-2-one (3e): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$; white solid (0.233 g, 83%); m.p. 132–133°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 3.73 (s, 3H), 4.33 (s, 2H), 5.28 (s, 1H), 6.45 (s, 1H), 7.12–7.31 (m, 6H), 7.62 (d, 2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 47.14, 56.12, 105.27, 115.79, 121.20, 124.29, 124.79, 125.55, 126.95, 127.35, 128.52, 132.48, 136.88, 147.32, 158.35; IR (KBr): 3307, 3083, 1761 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$: C, 72.58; H, 5.37; N, 4.98%. Found: C, 72.63; H, 5.35; N, 5.02%.

8-Methoxy-3-((4-methylbenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3f): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$; white solid (0.248 g, 84%); m.p. 140–142°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 2.38 (s, 3H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 4.33 (s, 2H), 5.29 (s, 1H), 6.36 (s, 1H), 7.13–7.15 (m, 2H), 7.33–7.43 (m, 4H), 7.74 (d, 1H, $J = 7.8$ Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 21.52, 47.11, 56.09, 105.25, 115.77, 121.22, 124.26, 124.76, 125.53, 126.97, 127.31, 128.52, 132.49, 136.79, 147.31, 158.32; IR (KBr): 3316, 3089, 1762 cm^{-1} ; ESI-MS Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$: $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 296.1281; Found: m/z 296.1285.

3-((4-Chlorobenzyl)amino)-8-methoxy-2H-chromen-2-one (3g): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_3$; white solid (0.274 g, 87%); m.p. 165–167°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 3.79 (s, 3H), 4.36 (s, 2H), 5.38 (s, 1H), 6.46 (s, 1H), 7.34–7.38 (m, 3H), 7.43 (d, 2H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 7.55 (d, 2H, $J = 8.4$ Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 47.48, 56.15, 105.68, 116.12, 121.60, 124.64, 125.15, 125.85, 127.37, 127.68,

128.88, 132.27, 137.26, 148.48, 160.27; IR (KBr): 3312, 3079, 1758 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_3$: C, 64.67; H, 4.47; N, 4.44%. Found: C, 64.69; H, 4.45; N, 4.49%.

8-Methoxy-3-((4-methoxybenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3h): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$; white solid (0.264 g, 85%); m.p. 155–157°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 3.77 (s, 6H), 4.28 (s, 2H), 5.26 (s, 1H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 7.18–7.20 (m, 2H), 7.26–7.31 (m, 2H), 7.46–7.53 (m, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 47.19, 56.45, 56.52, 105.29, 115.81, 121.22, 124.27, 124.79, 125.56, 126.97, 127.35, 128.55, 132.51, 136.89, 147.33, 158.37; IR (KBr): 3309, 3088, 1760 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$: C, 69.44; H, 5.50; N, 4.50%. Found: C, 69.42; H, 5.47; N, 4.55%.

3-(Benzylamino)-6-chloro-2H-chromen-2-one (3i): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_2$; white solid (0.239 g, 84%); m.p. 159–161°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 4.55 (s, 2H), 5.49 (s, 1H), 6.57 (s, 1H), 7.05–7.12 (m, 3H), 7.29 (t, 2H, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 7.75 (d, 2H, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 7.93 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 47.13, 105.27, 115.74, 121.23, 124.27, 124.79, 125.51, 126.97, 127.35, 128.52, 132.45, 136.89, 147.37, 159.22; IR (KBr): 3319, 3089, 1755 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_2$: C, 67.26; H, 4.23; N, 4.90%. Found: C, 67.29; H, 4.19; N, 4.94%.

6-Chloro-3-((4-methylbenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3j): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_2$; white solid (0.245 g, 82%); m.p. 152–154°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 2.36 (s, 3H), 4.56 (s, 2H), 5.53 (s, 1H), 6.63 (s, 1H), 7.28–7.30 (m, 4H), 7.57–7.59 (m, 2H), 8.03 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl_3 ; Me_4Si): δ 21.57, 47.46, 105.66, 116.05, 121.55, 124.61, 125.13, 125.85, 127.31, 127.66, 128.83, 132.25, 137.22, 148.30, 160.15; IR (KBr): 3312, 3079, 1760 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_2$: C, 68.12; H, 4.71; N, 4.67%. Found: C, 68.09; H, 4.69; N, 4.71%.

Kausar *et al.* : Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarins with primary aromatic *etc.*

6-Chloro-3-((4-chlorobenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3k) : Molecular formula : C₁₆H₁₁Cl₂NO₂; white solid (0.274 g, 86%); m.p. 202–204°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 4.57 (s, 2H), 5.53 (s, 1H), 6.62 (s, 1H), 7.29 (d, 2H, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 7.58 (d, 4H, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 8.04 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 47.48, 105.68, 116.08, 121.57, 124.64, 125.15, 125.88, 127.33, 127.67, 128.85, 132.28, 137.25, 148.33, 160.18; IR (KBr) : 3308, 3086, 1759 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁Cl₂NO₂ : C, 60.02; H, 3.46; N, 4.37%. Found : C, 60.05; H, 3.41; N, 4.42%.

6-Chloro-3-((4-methoxybenzyl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one (3l) : Molecular formula : C₁₆H₁₂ClNO₂; white solid (0.265 g, 84%); m.p. 168–170°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 3.62 (s, 3H), 4.36 (s, 2H), 5.36 (s, 1H), 6.39 (s, 1H), 7.10 (d, 1H, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 7.17 (d, 1H, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 7.34 (d, 2H, *J* = 7.5 Hz), 7.65 (d, 2H, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 8.04 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃; Me₄Si) : δ 47.42, 56.45, 105.63, 116.05, 121.58, 124.62, 125.12, 125.85, 127.31, 127.69, 128.84, 132.29, 137.25, 148.31, 160.14; IR (KBr) : 3311, 3078, 1755 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄ClNO₃ : [M+H]⁺, 316.0735; Found : *m/z* 316.0738.

Results and discussion

To study the possibility of our hypothesis for the N-benylation of various 3-aminocoumarin derivatives, 3-aminocoumarin (**1**) and benzylamine (**2**) were

chosen as the model substrate. Initially, 3-aminocoumarin (**1**) and benzylamine (**2**) were heated in DMSO or HOAc solvent under catalyst-free and NaN₃ free condition at 120°C but reaction did not proceed even after prolonged heating (Table 1, entries 1–2). After several unsuccessful attempts using Co(OAc)₂ (5 mol%) and CuCl₂ (5 mol%) catalysts (Table 1, entries 3–4) in DMSO medium, we performed the reaction in presence of CuCl₂ (5 mol%), NaN₃ (1 equiv.) in HOAc medium. In our delight, we got 35% yield of the product after heating 12 h at 120°C (Table 1, entry 6). Yield of the same reaction was further increased on employment of 2 equiv. of NaN₃ (Table 1, entry 7). It was found that yield of the reaction increased on increasing the catalyst loading from 5 mol% to 10 mol% at 100°C (Table 1, entry 8). Further increase in catalyst loading to 15 mol% led to a slight decrease in product yield (Table 1, entry 12).

The quantity of the catalyst here played a significant role in the formation of the desired product. The use of 5 mol% of Cu(OAc)₂ reduced the yield whereas the yield of the product also decreased when we used 15 mol% Cu(OAc)₂ (Table 1, entries 10 and 12). Few other Cu catalysts were also screened and Cu(OAc)₂ was found to be the most effective catalyst for the desired transformation. Next, we performed the same reaction under catalyst-free condition employing only NaN₃ (1 equiv.) in HOAc medium at 120°C (Table 1, entry 11). Interestingly,

Scheme 2. Benzylation of 3-aminocoumarins involving benzylamine and benzylalcohol.

Table 1. Optimization of reaction condition for the synthesis of 3-(benzylamino)-2*H*-chromen-2-one derivatives^a

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Yield ^b
1	–	DMSO	120	24	–
2	–	HOAc	120	24	–
3	Cu(OAc) ₂ (5 mol%)	DMSO	120	12	–
4	CuCl ₂ (5 mol%)	DMSO	120	12	–
5 ^c	CuCl ₂ (5 mol%)	DMSO	120	12	–
6 ^c	CuCl ₂ (5 mol%)	HOAc	120	12	35
7 ^d	CuCl ₂ (5 mol%)	HOAc	120	12	59
8 ^d	CuCl ₂ (5 mol%)	DMSO/HOAc	120	12	42
9 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (5 mol%)	HOAc	100	10	65
10 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (10 mol%)	HOAc	100	10	78
11 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (10 mol%)	HOAc	80	8	86
12 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (15 mol%)	HOAc	80	8	75
13 ^d	–	HOAc	120	12	–
14 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (10 mol%)	DMSO/HOAc (1 : 1)	80	8	72
15 ^d	Cu(OAc) ₂ (10 mol%)	dioxane/HOAc (1 : 1)	80	8	69

^aIn each case 3-aminocoumarin (1.0 mmol), benzylamine (1.2 mmol) and 1 mL of solvent were taken in a 25 mL rb flask.

^bYield of the isolated product. ^cReactions carried out in presence of NaN₃ (1 equiv.). ^dReactions carried out in presence of NaN₃ (2 equiv.).

reaction was unsuccessful in absence of Cu catalyst. It was confirmed that copper catalyst had a significant role for this transformation. The reaction was also monitored in different solvent systems and it is worth noting that reaction was completely blocked in absence of HOAc. Few other mixed solvent-systems (DMSO/HOAc or dioxane/HOAc) were also employed to perform the said reaction but HOAc was found to be most efficient reaction medium for this transformation. Finally, it was established that 10 mol% of Cu(OAc)₂ in HOAc medium at 80°C could furnish the best result within shortest period of time for the desired benzylation reaction (Table 1, entry 11). Hence, we chose this optimum reaction condition and successfully synthesized compound **3a-3l** (Table 2) in excellent yields.

The feasibility of our protocol was further explored by employing benzylalcohol (**4**) instead of benzylamine derivatives and substituted 3-aminocoumarin (**1**) under optimized reaction conditions. Interestingly, 3-(benzylamino)-2*H*-chromen-2-one derivatives were obtained in excellent yield (Table 3).

It is worth mentioning that the reaction was very clean producing only monobenzylated 3-aminocoumarin as the sole isolable product and no other side products were detected.

A plausible mechanism for this reaction is depicted in Scheme 4. At first, benzylamine/benzylalcohol converted into benzaldehyde (**1**). Then benzaldehyde (**1**) further reacted with 3-aminocoumarin (**2**) to produce an imine intermediate

Table 2. Substrate scope for the benzylation of 3-aminocoumarins involving benzylamine derivatives

Scheme 4. Plausible reaction pathway for the N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarins.

(II). In presence of HOAc, sodium azide converted into HN_3 and acted as mild reducing agent to produce the desired product (3). Cu(OAc)_2 played a vital role in this transformation and reaction was completely hampered when carried out in absence of Cu(OAc)_2 (Table 1, entry 13). The aerial oxidation process was assumed to be assisted by Cu(OAc)_2 ¹⁹.

Conclusions

In conclusion, a Cu^{II} -catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarin derivatives has been developed where benzylamine and benzylalcohol are used as benzylating agent. This protocol has several advan-

Table 3. Substrate scope for the benzylation of 3-aminocoumarins involving benzylalcohol

tages that include earth abundant metal catalysis, relatively shorter reaction time, relatively lower thermal energy, wide substrate scope and good to excellent yield.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the financial support from the centre of CAS-V (Synthesis and functional materials) of Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta for financial support. NK thanks DST, New Delhi, India for DST-inspire fellowship.

References

- (a) J. F. Hartwig, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2008, **41**, 1534; (b) D. S. Surry and S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 6338.
- R. P. Tripathi, S. S. Verma, J. Pandey and V. K. Tiwari, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **12**, 1093.
- R. Severin and S. Doye, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2007, **36**, 1407.
- R. Hili and A. K. Yudin, *Nat. Chem. Biol.*, 2006, **2**, 284.
- (a) Q. Yang, Q. Wang and Z. Yu, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2015, **44**, 2305; (b) G. E. Dobereiner and R. H. Crabtree, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 681; (c) M. H. S. A. Hamid, P. A. Slatford and J. M. J. Williams, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2007, **349**, 1555; (d) D. A. Surry and S. L. Buchwald, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 6338; (e) J. F. H. Hartwig, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2008, **41**, 1534; (f) K. Taguchi, H. Nakagawa, T. Hirabayashi, S. Sakaguchi and Y. Ishii, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 72.
- "Catalysis without Precious Metals", ed. R. M. Bullock, Wiley-VCH, Hoboken, NJ, 2010.
- R. N. Salvatore, C. H. Yoon and K. W. Jung, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 7785.
- D. Hollmann, S. Bahn, A. Tillack and M. Beller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, **46**, 8291.
- G. Zhang, Z. Yin and S. Zheng, *Org. Lett.*, 2016, **18**, 300.
- M. H. S. A. Hamid, C. L. Allen, G. W. Lamb and A. C. Maxwell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 1766.
- C. Liu, S. Liao, Q. Li, S. Feng, Q. Sun, X. Yu and Q. Xu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 5759.
- J. A. Burlison, L. Neckers, A. B. Smith, A. Maxwell and B. S. J. Blagg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 15529.
- (a) Z. Chen, L. Hu and F. Peng, *Synlett.*, 2016, DOI: 10.1055/s-0035-1561610; (b) A. A. H. Kadhum, A. B. Mohamad, A. A. Al-Amiery and M. S. Takriff, *Molecules*, 2011, **16**, 6969.
- (a) G. Le Bras, C. Radanyi, J.-F. Peyrat, J.-D. Brion, M. Alami, V. Marsaud, B. Stella and J.-M. Renoir, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **50**, 6189; (b) M. Belal and A. T. Khan, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**,

Kausar *et al.* : Cu(OAc)₂ catalyzed N-benylation of 3-aminocoumarins with primary aromatic *etc.*

- 104155; (c) J. A. Burlison, L. Neckers, A. B. Smith, A. Maxwell and B. S. J. Blagg. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 15529.
15. J. Li, D. Hu, X. Liang, Y. Wang, H. Wang and Y. Pan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2017, **82**, 9006.
16. K. C. Majumdar, B. Chattopadhyay and A. Taher, *Synthesis*, 2007, **23**, 3647.
17. M. A. Soussi, D. Audisio and S. Messaoudi, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **26**, 5077.
18. (a) N. Kausar and A. R. Das, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2017, **58**, 2602; (b) A. R. Das, A. Medda and R. Singha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 1099; (c) P. Bhattacharyya, A. Medda and A. R. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 623; (d) N. Kausar, A. A. Masum, M. M. Islam and A. R. Das, *Mol. Divers.*, 2017, DOI: 10.1007/s11030-017-9728-9.
19. (a) V. R. Choudhary, P. A. Chaudhari and V. S. Narkhede. *Catal. Commun.*, 2003, **4**, 171; (b) A. Dhakshinamoorthy, M. Alvaro and H. Garcia, *ACS Catal.*, 2011, **1**, 48; (c) P. J. Figiel, M. Leskelä and T. Repo, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2007, **349**, 1173.

